

**DENTAL HEALTH OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN:
RISK-ORIENTED ASSESSMENT OF CARIES AND
ENAMEL EROSION****Bebutov F.**

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The examined group is characterized by a dental health level typical for primary school children, moderate caries, the presence of early erosions, average oral hygiene quality, and predominantly normal functional parameters of oral fluid.

ABSTRACT

Diseases of the hard dental tissues in children, particularly caries and enamel erosion, remain a relevant dental problem. Caries develops under the influence of microorganisms, diet, oral hygiene habits, the composition and function of saliva, as well as fluoridation. Enamel erosion occurs as a result of acidic воздействия from external factors (acidic drinks and foods) and internal factors (gastroesophageal reflux, vomiting) not associated with bacterial activity. Saliva plays a key role in remineralization and protection of enamel; a decrease in its volume or buffering capacity increases the risk of lesions.

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Analysis of clinical data from 20 primary school children (mean age 8.5 ± 0.77 years) showed: BEWE index – 4.2 ± 0.41 , erosion prevalence – 34%, OHI-S – 1.7 ± 0.01 , API – 48%, total caries index DMFT/dmft ≈ 3.5 . The mean salivary pH was 6.8 ± 0.32 , buffering capacity – 6.0 ± 0.38 points, salivary flow rate – 0.45 ± 0.02 ml/min, subjective dryness – 18.5%. Risk distribution: low – 25%, moderate – 50%, high – 25%. Assigned prevention level: I – 28%, II – 52%, III – 20%.

A survey of dentists showed high agreement with clinical data: mean BEWE – 4.2 ± 2.8 , OHI-S – 1.7 ± 0.9 , API – $48 \pm 18\%$, salivary pH – 6.8 ± 0.3 , buffering capacity – 6.2 ± 0.64 , salivary flow rate – 0.45 ± 0.02 ml/min. A survey of children revealed gastrointestinal complaints and dietary habits contributing to erosion: heartburn – frequent 10%, occasional 30%; sour taste – 25%; pain/burning after eating – 50%; night eating (<1 hour before sleep) – 25%. Frequent consumption of acidic drinks and foods was noted in 35–45%, chewing gum/candies – 30%, limited drinking regimen – 20%. Oral hygiene behavior: brushing teeth ≥ 2 times per day – 60%, parental supervision – 25%. Tooth sensitivity to cold/acidic stimuli – 20% regularly, 40% episodically.

The overall integrated risk assessment showed: low – 30%, moderate – 45%, high – 25%, mean score – 7.8/20.

Based on the obtained results, the following measures can be recommended for children with GERD:

- **Low risk:** primary prevention, oral hygiene education, monitoring once a year.
- **Moderate risk:** secondary prevention, diet and fluoridation control, twice a year.
- **High risk:** individualized program, dietary correction, treatment of hypersensitivity, ≥ 2 times a year.

Conclusion: The examined group is characterized by a dental health level typical for primary school children, moderate caries, the presence of early erosions, average oral hygiene quality, and predominantly normal functional parameters of oral fluid. The data confirm the representativeness of the sample and the need for a personalized, risk-oriented approach to prevention..

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